

Consumer acceptance of different protein sources for meat alternatives: A multinational study

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ABSTRACT

A wide variety of alternative proteins have been proposed for use in meat alternatives; however, it is not known how their acceptance by consumers compares. In this study, the most promising protein sources for meat alternatives in terms of consumer acceptance were identified across four European countries. An online survey was conducted among meat-eating participants in Germany ($n = 472$), Finland ($n = 495$), Italy ($n = 498$), and Serbia ($n = 488$). The participants evaluated 14 different protein sources for meat alternatives, including a wide variety of plant-based proteins, algae, insects, and cultured meat, based on three dimensions: expected taste, expected healthiness, and expected environmental friendliness. In addition, the effect of food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat alternative rejection levels on the consumption of different types of meat alternatives was assessed. Potato, rice, and peas were identified as the most accepted protein sources across the four countries. The results also showed that consumers had low expectations for algae and cultured meat, and that insects were the least accepted. Furthermore, country-specific preferences for certain protein sources were observed.

1. Introduction

Meat consumption is linked to negative environmental impacts and animal welfare issues (Faucitano et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the average meat consumption in high-income countries continues to exceed the recommended dietary guidelines (Parlasca & Qaim, 2022). One strategy to reduce meat consumption and shift toward more sustainable diets is to substitute conventional meat with plant-based meat alternatives (Coffey et al., 2023). However, despite the substantial growth in the availability of meat alternatives in recent years, their total market share remains low (Good Food Institute [GFI], 2023). To illustrate, in 2022, plant-based meat alternatives accounted for only 6% of the total prepackaged meat market in Europe (Good Food Institute [GFI], 2023). While meat alternatives can be produced from a wide variety of protein sources, it remains unclear which protein sources are preferred by consumers across Europe. Since consumer acceptance plays an important role in the success of meat alternatives, it is essential to better understand consumers' expectations of different protein sources. Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify the most promising protein sources for meat alternatives, based on consumer expectations in four European countries.

1.1. Alternative protein sources as meat alternatives

Meat alternatives can be classified as traditional meat alternatives, new meat-like meat alternatives, and novel products. Traditional meat alternatives, such as tofu and falafel, refer to products that have been consumed for centuries and can serve as replacements for meat. Tofu, for example, is a staple food in the Asian diet and is now being used by some European consumers as a substitute for meat (Paz et al., 2021).

New meat-like meat alternatives represent a more recent generation of products that are designed to mimic the organoleptic characteristics of meat and are available in various shapes, including mince, burgers, and chunks (Arora et al., 2023). While these alternatives are often made from soy, wheat, or pea protein concentrates or isolates (van der Weele et al., 2019), a substantial body of research focuses on the use of alternative protein sources, including legumes, nuts, cereals, and oilseeds, in order to improve the nutritional properties, taste, texture, and meat-likeness (Sridhar et al., 2022).

In addition to these plant-based sources, the potential of novel proteins as meat alternatives is being explored; these include insects, algae, and cultured meat. Algae and insects offer nutritional and environmental advantages due to their high protein content and significantly lower land use compared to conventional livestock (Caporgno &

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Mathys, 2018; Van Huis et al., 2013). Although the consumption of algae and insects is more common in other parts of the world, these foods are considered novel in Europe (Regulation (EU) No 2015/2283). Cultured meat (i.e., in vitro cell cultivation) also shows great potential as a meat replacement, particularly with regard to its potential benefits for animal welfare and its capacity to reduce antibiotic use in agriculture (Post et al., 2020). However, the large-scale adoption of cultured meat remains uncertain due to technical, economic, and regulatory challenges (Post et al., 2020).

1.2. Consumer acceptance of alternative protein sources

Despite the growing interest in alternative proteins, several barriers must be overcome to increase consumer acceptance (Onwezen et al., 2021; Siegrist & Hartmann, 2023). One of the most significant challenges is addressing low sensory expectations, particularly regarding taste. This has been shown to be a major obstacle to the acceptance of plant-based meat alternatives, algae, and cultured meat (Michel, Knaapila, et al., 2021a; Verbeke et al., 2015). In the case of insects, feelings of disgust appear to be an additional factor hindering acceptance (La Barbera et al., 2018). Along with sensory concerns, consumers' healthiness and environmental perceptions have been shown to play an important role. While alternative proteins are typically promoted as more sustainable and nutritious than conventional meat, consumers do not always perceive them as such. For example, Hartmann et al. (2022) demonstrated that plant-based meat alternatives are often perceived as less healthy and less environmentally friendly than conventional meat. Consumers tend to associate these products with high levels of processing, which negatively influences their naturalness and healthiness perceptions (Hartmann et al., 2022). Furthermore, cultured meat is also often viewed as less healthy than conventional meat due to its perceived unnaturalness and associated disgust (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020).

Psychological factors have also been shown to influence acceptance. Several studies have found a negative correlation between food neophobia (i.e., the reluctance to consume unfamiliar foods (Pliner & Hobden, 1992)) and consumers' willingness to consume plant-based meat alternatives, algae, insects, and cultured meat (de Koning et al., 2020; Dupont & Fiebelkorn, 2020; La Barbera et al., 2018; Michel, Hartmann, & Siegrist, 2021b). Furthermore, high levels of meat commitment have been associated with lower intentions to reduce meat consumption or replace meat with meat alternatives (Etter et al., 2024; Knaapila et al., 2022). In addition to the aforementioned perceptions of meat alternatives being inferior to conventional meat, consumers' food neophobia and rigid meat-eating habits, the low acceptance of meat alternatives has been linked to skepticism toward meat alternatives, as measured with the meat alternative rejection scale (Wassmann et al., 2025).

Although the acceptance of alternative proteins remains relatively low (Onwezen et al., 2021), it has been found that in Western countries, plant-based proteins are more widely accepted than other alternative protein sources, including, algae (Michel, Knaapila, et al., 2021a), insects (de Koning et al., 2020), and cultured meat (Bryant & Dillard, 2019; Slade, 2018). However, most consumer studies on the acceptance of alternative proteins have focused on individual protein sources or compared a limited number of alternatives. In order to gain a better understanding of why some proteins are accepted and others are not, there is a need for direct comparisons across multiple protein sources and across countries (Onwezen et al., 2021).

1.3. The role of food culture

A recent study by Etter et al. (2024) made a significant contribution to the field by directly comparing the acceptance of various alternative protein sources for meat alternatives in Switzerland. The study identified potato, lentils, and peas as the most promising sources and cultured meat as the least promising. However, these findings may not be

generalizable across Europe, as consumer expectations likely vary due to differences in culinary traditions and familiarity with certain protein sources (Etter et al., 2024). For instance, the cultural importance of potatoes in traditional Swiss dishes (e.g., rösti) could explain the favorable attitudes toward potatoes in Switzerland, whereas they may be judged differently in other countries. To address this gap, the present study compares consumer expectations regarding 14 alternative protein sources for meat alternatives across four countries: Finland, Serbia, Italy, and Germany, which represent the north, east, south, and west of Europe, respectively. These countries were selected based on their geographic diversity and distinct culinary traditions.

Meat consumption has long been central to European food cultures, driven not only by nutritional needs or agricultural sustainability but also by cultural identity (Chiles & Fitzgerald, 2017). Regional factors such as climate, geography, and economic conditions have shaped distinct food consumption patterns across Europe (Grigg, 1993). Italy, for example, represents the Mediterranean diet, which is rich in olive oil, fruits, and vegetables, reflecting the region's agricultural landscape. In contrast, Finland and Germany have traditionally relied more on meat and dairy products due to their extensive grazing lands and distinct northern and western European climates. The food culture in Serbia, situated in the eastern region of Europe, can be described as an intermediate between Mediterranean and northern European food culture, with meat and dairy remaining essential components (Krsteva-Blagoeva & Bogueva, 2021). Despite the increasing homogeneity in European diets through globalization, regional differences in dietary patterns remain evident (de Boer et al., 2006).

1.4. Aim of the present study

The aim of the present study is to identify the most promising protein sources for the use in meat alternatives based on consumers' expectations regarding taste, healthiness, and environmental friendliness. In order to examine whether consumer expectations differ across Europe, the study compares four countries representing the north, east, south and west: Finland, Serbia, Italy, and Germany. Furthermore, the study examines how consumer characteristics, including food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat alternative rejection, influence the consumption of traditional and new meat-like meat alternatives.

2. Methods

2.1. Sampling and participants

The data for this study was collected in November and December 2023 via an online survey in Germany, Finland, Italy, and Serbia. The participants were recruited through a commercial panel provider (Bilendi & ResponDi AG, Cologne, Germany) and were compensated in accordance with the panel provider's reimbursement policy. In order to participate in the study, respondents had to be at least 20 years of age. Quotas were set to achieve an equal distribution of both sexes and age groups (20–29, 30–39, 40–49, 50–59, 60+ years). This study exclusively focused on meat eaters (i.e., omnivores or flexitarians), as this is the target group of the dietary shift. Therefore, data from non-meat eaters (i.e., respondents who indicated that their dietary style could best be described as pescetarian, vegetarian, or vegan) were excluded from the dataset ($n = 108$). After excluding incomplete responses ($n = 45$), and responses with a completion time of less than half of the median duration ($n = 216$), the total sample included 1953 participants. Of the total sample, 472 participants were from Germany, 495 from Finland, 498 from Italy, and 488 from Serbia. Table 1 presents the characteristics of the participants in each country sample.

2.2. Survey procedure

The survey was initially written in English and subsequently

Table 1
Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants per country sample (number of participants (percentage)).

		Germany (n = 472)	Finland (n = 495)	Italy (n = 498)	Serbia (n = 488)
Age	Mean (SD)	47 (15)	46 (15)	46 (15)	45 (15)
Sex	Male	255 (54%)	250 (51%)	275 (55%)	240 (49%)
	Female	217 (46%)	245 (49%)	223 (45%)	248 (51%)
Education level	No degree	2 (<1%)	12 (2%)	0 (0%)	1 (<1%)
	Compulsory	31 (7%)	32 (6%)	154 (31%)	141 (29%)
	Further education	324 (69%)	381 (77%)	230 (46%)	186 (38%)
	Higher education	115 (24%)	70 (14%)	114 (23%)	160 (33%)
Dietary style	Omnivores	298 (63%)	448 (91%)	416 (84%)	343 (70%)
	Flexitarians	174 (37%)	47 (9%)	82 (16%)	145 (30%)

translated into German, Finnish, Italian, and Serbian through a forward-and-backward translation process conducted by two independent translators. The back-translations were then reviewed and compared with the original English version to ensure that the intended meaning was accurately conveyed. The survey was programmed using Qualtrics software (Qualtrics, Provo, UT, USA).

Prior to participation, subjects were presented with a brief introductory text that outlined the objectives of the study and were asked to provide informed consent. Subsequently, sociodemographic data, including sex, age, and educational level, as well as information on the self-identified dietary style of the participants was collected. The response options for dietary style were provided along with a definition of each term: omnivore (I regularly eat meat), flexitarian (I only eat meat rarely), pescetarian (I do not eat meat, but fish and seafood), vegetarian (I eat neither meat nor fish and seafood), and vegan (I eat no animal-based products at all). The remaining portion of the survey was divided into two sections. The first section comprised a rating task of various protein sources for meat alternatives. The second section included questions on food consumption behavior.

2.2.1. Protein source rating task

This section of the survey commenced with an introduction page on which participants were provided with the following definition of meat alternatives: "Meat alternatives are designed to allow consumers to prepare meals without the need for meat. They contain proteins from alternative sources and imitate the characteristics of traditional meat products in terms of taste, texture, and appearance. At the same time, the nutritional values they contain should be comparable to meat." Subsequently, participants evaluated 14 protein sources for the use in meat alternatives based on taste, healthiness, and environmental friendliness expectations. For each dimension, participants responded to a question (e.g., "How tasty do you expect meat alternatives made from the following proteins and protein sources to be?") using a semantic differential continuous slider ranging from 0 (not tasty at all) to 100 (very tasty). It is important to note that participants were asked to rate the protein sources as processed into meat alternatives (e.g., pea-based meat alternatives), rather than as whole foods. The order of protein sources was randomized, and the rating task was repeated for each dimension separately.

The decision to focus on only three dimensions was based on the findings of [Etter et al. \(2024\)](#), who identified high intercorrelations among six dimensions measuring acceptance of alternative protein sources. Taste was selected because it is often mentioned as the most important factor in food choices ([Onwezen et al., 2019](#); [Steptoe & Pollard, 1995](#)). Healthiness and environmental friendliness were selected because they represent key motivations for users of meat alternatives, although these perceptions are not necessarily shared by all consumers ([Hartmann et al., 2022](#)) or across all types of meat alternatives ([Siegrist & Hartmann, 2023](#)). The participants were not provided with definitions for the three dimensions, leaving this open to their own interpretation. As a result, responses were based on their individual beliefs, experiences, and knowledge.

2.2.2. Selection of protein sources

To enable direct comparisons across different categories of alternative protein sources, a diverse set of protein sources was selected, encompassing plant-based proteins, algae, insects, and cultured meat. The plant-based proteins included various legumes (faba bean, soy, peas, and lentils), cereals (rice and oats), nuts (almond), tubers (potato), and oilseeds (rapeseed and sunflower). The general term "algae" was used since participants may not be familiar with specific types of algae. Crickets were selected to represent insects because they are the most common type of edible insect ([Florenca et al., 2022](#)). Furthermore, the present study focused exclusively on cultured beef, since consumers generally do not differentiate between different types of cultured meat ([Etter et al., 2024](#)). Finally, chicken egg was included as an animal-based non-meat reference.

This selection of 14 protein sources includes sources with varying degrees of familiarity, availability, and accessibility. Some protein sources are well known to most European consumers (e.g., most plant-based sources), while others are less familiar (e.g., algae and crickets) or currently unavailable in Europe (e.g., cultured beef).

2.2.3. Food consumption behavior

The final section of the survey included questions related to participants' food consumption behavior. It included questions on food consumption frequency and the constructs of food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat alternative rejection.

Food consumption frequency was assessed by asking the participants the following question: "How often do you consume the following foods?" The categories included meat, traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel), and new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks). Responses were provided on a 5-point scale (1 = daily, 2 = 4–6 times per week, 3 = 1–3 times per week, 4 = 1–3 times per month, and 5 = rarely or never).

Food neophobia (i.e., the reluctance to consume new or unfamiliar foods) was measured using the original 10-item food neophobia scale developed by [Pliner and Hobden \(1992\)](#). The scale includes items such as "I do not trust new foods" and "I am afraid to eat things I have never had before". Responses were measured on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 = do not agree at all to 7 = fully agree.

Meat commitment was evaluated using the 7-item scale developed by [Piazza et al. \(2015\)](#). This scale assesses the importance individuals attach to the meat portion in a meal and their (un)willingness to reduce meat consumption, and includes items such as "I would never give up eating meat" and "the best part of most meals is the meat portion". Items were measured on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 = do not agree at all to 7 = fully agree.

Meat alternative rejection was measured using the 10-item meat alternative rejection scale, developed by [Wassmann et al. \(2025\)](#). This scale assesses (dis)beliefs in the potential benefits of meat alternatives with regard to animal welfare, environment, and health as well as the ability of these alternatives to adequately replace meat. A few examples of items are "meat substitutes are not environmentally friendly" and "meat substitutes are only a temporary trend". The items were measured on a 7-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from 1 = do not agree

at all to 7 = fully agree.

Although the meat commitment and meat alternative rejection scales are correlated (Wassmann et al., 2025), the items measure distinct constructs (i.e., the commitment to eating meat versus the rejection of meat alternatives). While consumers with high meat commitment scores often also tend to be skeptical of meat alternatives, the meat alternative rejection scale has been shown to better detect differences in consumers' perceptions of meat alternatives (Wassmann et al., 2025). For this reason, both scales were included in the present study.

Negative items were recoded and mean scores of food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat alternative rejection were calculated for each participant. Cronbach's alpha values indicated that all scales exhibited good reliability ($\alpha > .70$) across the four country samples (see Table 2).

2.3. Data analysis

Three independent repeated-measures ANOVAs ($p = .05$) were performed to assess the effect of protein source and country on participants' expectations regarding the taste, healthiness, and environmental friendliness of meat alternatives. Mauchly's test indicated that the assumption of sphericity had been violated, thereby necessitating correction of the degrees of freedom using Greenhouse-Geisser estimates of sphericity ($\epsilon < .75$). The means and 95% confidence intervals of the three dimensions (expected taste, expected healthiness, and expected environmental friendliness) were compared across the protein sources to identify the most and least promising ones in terms of consumer acceptance in each country. The confidence intervals were calculated by using the Cousineau-Morey adjustment for a within-subjects design (Baguley, 2012), which enabled comparisons between the different protein sources within each country sample.

Further, two logistic regressions were conducted for each country sample to assess the influence of consumer characteristics on the consumption of traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel) and new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks) as well as to investigate whether this varies by country. The consumption of meat alternatives was coded as 0 = never or rarely and 1 = at least once per month. The predictors included in the regression models were age, sex, food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat alternative rejection. A correlation analysis was conducted on the study variables (Table 4).

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics, Version 29.0 (IBM Corp. Armonk, NY, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Protein source ratings for meat alternatives

The mean scores and 95% confidence intervals of participants' expectations regarding the taste, healthiness, and environmental friendliness of the different protein sources for meat alternatives are presented separately for each country in Figs. 1–3.

The results of the repeated-measures ANOVA indicated a statistically significant effect of protein source on the taste expectations of meat alternatives ($F(9.31, 18134.53) = 753.25, p < .001$). Moreover, significant differences were found across countries ($F(3, 1949) = 18.21, p < .001$). The interaction between protein source and country was also

significant ($F(27.91, 18134.53) = 30.50, p < .001$). In all countries, chicken egg was expected to be the most or second-most tasty protein source for meat alternatives. Among the alternative sources, potato, rice, and peas received high scores across all countries. In addition, country-specific preferences were observed. Almond was highly rated in Germany and Serbia, oats in Finland, and lentils in Italy. It is noteworthy that cultured beef received particularly high ratings in Germany, where its taste expectations were significantly higher than those of most other protein sources. Further, crickets and algae were expected to be the least tasty protein sources in all countries, along with soy in Germany, sunflower in Finland, and rapeseed in Italy and Serbia.

Furthermore, significant differences in expected healthiness were observed across protein sources ($F(9.30, 18117.19) = 477.91, p < .001$). The results also indicated significant differences across countries ($F(3, 1949) = 3.75, p < .001$). The interaction between protein source and country was also significant ($F(27.89, 18117.19) = 34.16, p < .001$). Similarly, the expected environmental friendliness of meat alternatives differed significantly by protein source ($F(8.44, 16442.05) = 274.04, p < .001$). The country once again had a significant effect ($F(3, 1949) = 13.27, p < .001$), and the interaction between protein source and country was again significant ($F(25.31, 16442.05) = 36.56, p < .001$).

The results concerning expectations of healthiness and environmental friendliness were less clear-cut than those related to taste. However, the ratings for these two dimensions were generally higher than those for taste. A few of the proteins with the highest taste expectations (including potato, peas, lentils, and oat) were also among those with the highest healthiness and environmental friendliness expectations. Moreover, country differences were observed. Despite their high taste ratings across all countries, participants in Germany and Finland considered chicken egg, rice, and almond to be among the least environmentally friendly sources, whereas in Italy and Serbia, these protein sources were viewed as among the most environmentally friendly.

Across all countries, crickets and cultured beef were among the lowest-rated protein sources in terms healthiness and environmental friendliness expectations. Additionally, algae and rapeseed received low healthiness ratings in all countries, along with soy in Germany and Finland. In terms of environmental friendliness, algae and rapeseed received again low ratings in Italy and Serbia, while this applied to rice and soy in Germany and Finland.

3.2. Food consumption behavior

The majority of participants from the four countries (56%–61%) indicated that they rarely or never consume traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel). Similar figures were found for new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks) in Germany and Finland, where 54%–59% of the participants rarely or never consume these products. In contrast, 67%–68% of the Italian and Serbian participants indicated that they consume new meat-like meat alternatives at least once per month (Table 3). Overall, meat is consumed significantly more often than meat alternatives in all countries. The highest meat consumption was observed in Finland and Serbia, where most participants consume meat four to six times per week (34%–35%) or daily (27%–28%). In Germany and Italy, the majority of participants (46%–59%) reported consuming meat only one to three times per week.

Table 2

Mean and reliability scores of participants' food neophobia, meat commitment, and meat alternative rejection levels per country sample (ranging from 1 to 7).

	Germany ($n = 472$)		Finland ($n = 495$)		Italy ($n = 498$)		Serbia ($n = 488$)	
	Mean (SD)	α	Mean (SD)	α	Mean (SD)	α	Mean (SD)	α
Food neophobia	3.4 (1.1)	.82	3.3 (1.2)	.89	3.8 (1.1)	.83	3.5 (1.0)	.76
Meat commitment	4.2 (1.6)	.92	4.3 (1.7)	.95	3.9 (1.5)	.94	4.3 (1.7)	.93
Meat alternative rejection	4.1 (1.5)	.93	4.0 (1.4)	.94	4.1 (1.5)	.95	4.3 (1.6)	.94

Note: α = Cronbach's alpha.

Table 3
Consumption frequency of meat, traditional meat alternatives, and new meat-like meat alternatives per country sample (number of participants (percentage)).

	Germany (n = 472)			Finland (n = 495)			Italy (n = 498)			Serbia (n = 488)		
	Meat	Traditional MA ^a	Meat-like MA ^b	Meat	Traditional MA ^a	Meat-like MA ^b	Meat	Traditional MA ^a	Meat-like MA ^b	Meat	Traditional MA ^a	Meat-like MA ^b
Daily	47 (10%)	8 (2%)	10 (2%)	141 (28%)	6 (1%)	12 (2%)	39 (8%)	6 (1%)	8 (2%)	133 (27%)	10 (2%)	21 (4%)
4–6 times per week	137 (29%)	24 (5%)	28 (6%)	173 (35%)	13 (3%)	21 (4%)	86 (17%)	24 (5%)	28 (6%)	164 (34%)	21 (4%)	49 (10%)
1–3 times per week	216 (46%)	82 (17%)	76 (16%)	144 (29%)	70 (14%)	74 (15%)	292 (59%)	92 (19%)	147 (29%)	141 (29%)	75 (15%)	120 (25%)
1–3 times per month	66 (14%)	92 (20%)	103 (22%)	29 (6%)	106 (21%)	95 (19%)	62 (12%)	85 (17%)	149 (30%)	38 (8%)	103 (21%)	143 (29%)
Rarely or never	6 (1%)	266 (56%)	255 (54%)	8 (2%)	300 (61%)	293 (59%)	19 (4%)	291 (58%)	166 (33%)	12 (2%)	279 (57%)	155 (32%)

^a Traditional meat alternatives (MA) include tofu, falafel, etc.

^b New meat-like meat alternatives (MA) include plant-based mince, burgers, chunks, etc.

Table 4
Pearson’s correlation between study variables per country sample.

		Germany (n = 472)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Age		1						
2	Sex ^a		.03	1					
3	Food neophobia		.11*	.06	1				
4	Meat commitment		.03	-.20**	.24**	1			
5	Meat alternative rejection		.16**	-.04	.39**	.65**	1		
6	Traditional MA consumption ^b		-.34**	-.06	-.31**	-.24**	-.29**	1	
7	New meat-like MA consumption ^c		-.34**	-.08	-.21**	-.19**	-.30**	.60**	1
Finland (n = 495)									
1	Age		1						
2	Sex ^a		-.01	1					
3	Food neophobia		-.04	.08	1				
4	Meat commitment		-.11*	-.23**	.23**	1			
5	Meat alternative rejection		.05	-.15**	.26**	.68**	1		
6	Traditional MA consumption ^b		-.15**	-.01	-.21**	-.44**	-.37**	1	
7	New meat-like MA consumption ^c		-.07	-.06	-.07	-.20**	-.14**	.45**	1
Italy (n = 498)									
1	Age		1						
2	Sex ^a		.03	1					
3	Food neophobia		.29**	.04	1				
4	Meat commitment		-.10*	-.17**	.10*	1			
5	Meat alternative rejection		.14**	-.05	.45**	.59**	1		
6	Traditional MA consumption ^b		-.20**	-.03	-.20**	-.13**	-.18**	1	
7	New meat-like MA consumption ^c		-.14**	-.02	-.02	.04	-.06	.30**	1
Serbia (n = 488)									
1	Age		1						
2	Sex ^a		-.03	1					
3	Food neophobia		.06	.02	1				
4	Meat commitment		-.11*	-.19**	.13**	1			
5	Meat alternative rejection		.02	-.14**	.20**	.60**	1		
6	Traditional MA consumption ^b		-.12*	.03	-.11*	-.29**	-.28**	1	
7	New meat-like MA consumption ^c		-.21**	-.09*	-.06	.02	-.12**	.28**	1

Note: Correlations are significant at * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$.

^a Sex: 0 = male, 1 = female.

^b Traditional meat alternative (MA) consumption: 0 = never or rarely, 1 = at least once per month.

^c New meat-like meat alternative (MA) consumption: 0 = never or rarely, 1 = at least once per month.

Furthermore, the four countries demonstrated notable differences in personality traits related to food consumption behavior. On average, participants in Italy exhibited the highest levels of food neophobia. Meat commitment levels were highest in Finland and Serbia, and lowest in Italy. Finally, the highest meat alternative rejection levels were also found in Serbia, while they were comparable across the other three countries (Table 2).

3.3. Drivers for meat alternative consumption

All logistic regression models predicting the consumption of traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel) and new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks) were statistically significant (Table 5). The models showed an improvement in fit over the null model, with Nagelkerke R^2 values ranging from .11 to .35 for the consumption of traditional meat alternatives, and from .04 to .25 for the

consumption of new meat-like meat alternatives.

In general, younger participants were more likely to consume both traditional and new meat-like meat alternatives compared to older participants. Sex had a significant effect on the consumption of both types of meat alternatives in Finland, and on that of new meat-like meat alternatives in Serbia; in these two countries, males were more likely to consume meat alternatives than females.

In all four countries, a strong association was observed between the consumption of traditional meat alternatives and meat commitment. The association was negative, which indicates that individuals with lower levels of meat commitment were more likely to consume traditional meat alternatives. In Finland, a higher consumption of new meat-like meat alternatives was also associated with lower meat commitment levels, while in the other three countries, no significant effect was observed. In Germany and Serbia, the consumption of new meat-like meat alternatives was negatively influenced by meat alternative

Fig. 1. Comparison of the expected taste ratings of protein sources for meat alternatives in Germany ($n = 472$), Finland ($n = 495$), Italy ($n = 498$), and Serbia ($n = 488$). Note: Non-overlapping confidence intervals indicate significant differences of means within country samples ($p < .05$).

Fig. 2. Comparison of the expected healthiness ratings of protein sources for meat alternatives in Germany ($n = 472$), Finland ($n = 495$), Italy ($n = 498$), and Serbia ($n = 488$). Note: Non-overlapping confidence intervals indicate significant differences of means within country samples ($p < .05$).

rejection levels, and this also applied to the consumption of traditional meat alternatives in Serbia. In Finland and Italy, meat alternative rejection levels did not show any significant effect.

Furthermore, individuals with lower levels of food neophobia were more likely to consume traditional meat alternatives in all countries except Serbia. In contrast, food neophobia did not significantly affect the consumption of new meat-like meat alternatives in Finland, Italy, and Serbia. An exception to this trend was observed in Germany, where food

neophobia was a significant predictor for the consumption of both traditional and new meat-like meat alternatives.

4. Discussion

The overall aim of the present study was to identify the most promising protein sources for meat alternatives based on consumers' taste, healthiness, and environmental friendliness expectations in

Fig. 3. Comparison of the expected environmental friendliness ratings of protein sources for meat alternatives in Germany ($n = 472$), Finland ($n = 495$), Italy ($n = 498$), and Serbia ($n = 488$). Note: Non-overlapping confidence intervals indicate significant differences of means within country samples ($p < .05$).

Table 5

Results from the logistic regressions predicting the consumption frequency of traditional and new meat-like meat alternatives per country sample: never or rarely (coded 0) vs. at least once per month (coded 1).

	Germany ($n = 472$)			Finland ($n = 495$)			Italy ($n = 498$)			Serbia ($n = 488$)		
	B	OR	95% CI (OR)	B	OR	95% CI (OR)	B	OR	95% CI (OR)	B	OR	95% CI (OR)
Consumption of traditional MA ^a	$\chi^2(6) = 122.26, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .31$			$\chi^2(6) = 147.40, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .35$			$\chi^2(6) = 41.36, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .11$			$\chi^2(6) = 63.84, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .17$		
Age	-.05***	0.95	[0.94, 0.96]	-.04***	0.96	[0.95, 0.98]	-.02***	0.98	[0.96, 0.99]	-.02**	0.98	[0.97, 0.99]
Sex ^b	-.36	0.70	[0.45, 1.07]	-.65**	0.52	[0.33, 0.82]	-.19	0.83	[0.57, 1.21]	-.17	0.85	[0.57, 1.26]
Food neophobia	-.55***	0.58	[0.46, 0.73]	-.25*	0.78	[0.64, 0.95]	-.26*	0.77	[0.63, 0.95]	-.11	0.90	[0.74, 1.10]
Meat commitment	-.24**	0.78	[0.65, 0.94]	-.64***	0.53	[0.44, 0.63]	-.17*	0.84	[0.72, 0.99]	-.30***	0.74	[0.64, 0.86]
Meat alternative rejection	-.11	0.90	[0.74, 1.09]	-.13	0.88	[0.72, 1.09]	-.05	0.96	[0.80, 1.14]	-.19*	0.83	[0.72, 0.96]
Constant	5.52***	248.78		5.52***	249.23		2.64***	14.02		3.21***	24.76	
Consumption of new meat-like MA ^b	$\chi^2(6) = 98.83, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .25$			$\chi^2(6) = 32.28, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .09$			$\chi^2(6) = 13.04, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .04$			$\chi^2(6) = 35.88, p < .001,$ Nagelkerke $R^2 = .10$		
Age	-.05***	0.96	[0.94, 0.97]	-.02*	0.99	[0.97, 1.00]	-.02**	0.98	[0.97, 1.00]	-.03***	0.97	[0.96, 0.98]
Sex ^c	-.39	0.68	[0.45, 1.03]	-.48*	0.62	[0.42, 0.91]	-.06	0.94	[0.64, 1.39]	-.46*	0.63	[0.42, 0.95]
Food neophobia	-.21*	0.81	[0.66, 1.00]	-.03	0.97	[0.83, 1.15]	.11	1.12	[0.91, 1.36]	-.05	0.95	[0.78, 1.17]
Meat commitment	-.06	0.94	[0.79, 1.12]	-.33***	0.72	[0.62, 0.84]	.12	1.12	[0.95, 1.32]	.11	1.12	[0.97, 1.30]
Meat alternative rejection	-.32**	0.73	[0.60, 0.89]	.05	1.05	[0.88, 1.26]	-.16	0.85	[0.71, 1.02]	-.24**	0.79	[0.67, 0.92]
Constant	4.42***	83.42		1.82***	6.17		1.38**	3.96		3.10***	22.29	

Note: Values in bold are significant at * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

^a Traditional meat alternatives (MA) include tofu, falafel, etc.

^b New meat-like meat alternatives (MA) include plant-based mince, burgers, chunks, etc.

^c Sex: 0 = male, 1 = female.

Germany, Finland, Italy, and Serbia. The findings indicate that expectations regarding taste are more nuanced than those concerning health and environmental friendliness. This may be attributed to the fact that taste expectations are typically shaped by personal preferences and experiences, whereas health and environmental evaluations require a more profound understanding and knowledge. People often rely on simplified assumptions and heuristics instead. As shown by Lazzarini et al. (2016), perceptions of healthiness and environmental friendliness are often based on broad product categories, such as the distinction between meat and plant-based products. Additional cues, such as labels, degree of processing, and country of origin, also influence these perceptions (Lazzarini et al., 2016). Moreover, consumers frequently use

the “natural-is-better” heuristic when evaluating the healthiness and environmental friendliness of products (Hartmann et al., 2022). This heuristic is a mental shortcut in which people tend to perceive foods they consider “natural”, primarily based on the perceived degree of processing, as better and more desirable (Hartmann et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, the findings indicated that participants in Germany and Finland were more critical of the environmental friendliness of protein sources than participants in Italy and Serbia. For example, they seemed to be more aware of the environmental impact of chicken egg, rice, and almond. This assumption is correct, as rice and almonds require larger amounts of water compared to other crops (Lovarelli et al., 2016). These results suggest a higher level of environmental awareness in these

countries, which is consistent with earlier research showing that populations in northern Europe are more environmentally aware than those in other parts of Europe (Bacsi, 2020).

4.1. Most promising protein sources for meat alternatives

Across all countries, chicken egg was overall the most accepted protein source, while potato, rice, and peas were identified as the most promising among the alternative protein sources. These protein sources have also been identified as popular among consumers in Switzerland (Etter et al., 2024). Due to their longstanding presence in the European diet, most participants are familiar with these ingredients. Since familiarity plays an essential role in consumer perceptions of novel foods (Tuorila & Hartmann, 2020), this has likely contributed to their greater acceptance for the use in meat alternatives. Furthermore, the present study confirmed previous findings that plant-based protein sources are more widely accepted than algae (Michel, Knaapila, et al., 2021b), insects (de Koning et al., 2020), and cultured meat (Bryant & Dillard, 2019).

In addition, oats were particularly well-accepted in Finland, almonds in Germany and Serbia, and lentils in Italy. These country-specific preferences may be explained by local culinary traditions and exposure, which have been demonstrated to play a crucial role in food acceptance and preferences (Giacalone & Jaeger, 2023; Hoek et al., 2011; Tuorila & Hartmann, 2020). For instance, Finland is one of the main oat producers in the EU (Mäkelä & Rautavirta, 2018) and has recently experienced an increase in oat-based products, including pulled oats, a popular Finnish plant-based meat substitute. This high level of exposure may have contributed to the preference for oats in Finland. Similarly, legumes are a staple crop in Mediterranean agriculture and lentils have been cultivated in Italy since ancient times (Piergiovanni, 2021). Furthermore, lentils are used in several traditional Italian recipes (Piergiovanni, 2021), which may explain their high acceptance in the country.

The results show that not all plant-based sources were highly accepted. Across all countries, rapeseed and sunflower received low scores for expected taste, healthiness, and environmental friendliness. The fact that these ingredients are widely produced across Europe, and thus well-known to most consumers, suggests that familiarity and exposure do not always lead to high acceptance rates. As rapeseed and sunflower are commonly used as cooking oils, they may be associated with fat rather than protein sources and therefore perceived as unsuitable ingredients for meat alternatives. The same can be argued for starchy sources such as potatoes and rice; however, these sources were more widely accepted than oilseeds. This difference may be because consumers often perceive fat as a less healthy and less desirable ingredient than starch and protein (de Araujo et al., 2022). Moreover, many countries have traditional dishes that are rich in starch, which is considered a primary meal component alongside protein and vegetables. This could also explain the higher acceptance of starches compared to fats.

Another protein source that was perceived as less acceptable was soy. Despite its health effects, consumers in Western countries often have negative attitudes toward soy (Fenko et al., 2015; Tu et al., 2012). Several factors have been identified that contribute to these perceptions, including a negative taste image (Wansink, 2003), associations with genetically modified organisms (Tu et al., 2012), and limited familiarity with soy-based products (Fenko et al., 2015). However, soy is potentially perceived more positively in Asian cultures, where it is more integrated into traditional diets.

Since consumers are generally reluctant to change their dietary habits, a shift away from meat toward plant-based proteins is unlikely in the short term (Siegrist et al., 2024). To achieve broader acceptance, the taste and texture of plant-based meat alternatives must be improved and aligned with consumer preferences. The findings of the present study demonstrate that the protein source exerts a significant influence on

consumer expectations of meat alternatives and should therefore be considered in new product development. For example, strategic selection and labeling of already accepted protein sources by product developers and marketers has the potential to enhance the appeal of meat alternatives and facilitate their wider acceptance.

4.2. Consumer acceptance of insects, algae, and cultured meat

While cultured meat was identified as the least accepted protein source among Swiss consumers (Etter et al., 2024), crickets were the least accepted among participants of the present study. This can be attributed to the fact that eating insects is not part of European culture and often evokes feelings of disgust (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2016; La Barbera et al., 2018). This aversion is reflected by the low taste expectations for crickets reported in the present study. Furthermore, the potential health and environmental benefits of substituting meat with insects (Van Huis et al., 2013) were not perceived by the participants, which may represent an additional barrier to the adoption of insects across Europe.

Algae was perceived as healthier and more environmentally friendly than cultured beef and crickets in all countries. However, the taste expectations for algae were relatively low. Again, this could be attributed to the limited familiarity with algae as a food source in Europe (Mellor et al., 2022; Weickert et al., 2021). Moreover, it is possible that consumers associate algae with a fishy taste, which may negatively affect its appeal as meat alternative. Given that the participants were aware of the health and environmental benefits of algae, these attributes should be emphasized when promoting algae-based products.

Cultured beef, despite being perceived as less healthy and less environmentally friendly, was expected to taste better than crickets and algae. Studies have shown that meat eaters tend to prefer meat alternatives that resemble meat more closely (Hoek et al., 2011; Michel, Hartmann, & Siegrist, 2021a). Since cultured meat aims to mimic the sensory properties of meat, this similarity could be perceived as a positive attribute. However, the acceptance of cultured meat varies across cultures and, in certain countries, the perceived unnaturalness and disgust evoked by cultured meat represent significant barriers (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020). Country differences were also observed in the present study. In Germany, taste expectations for cultured beef were significantly higher than in the other countries, exceeding those of most plant-based sources. This could suggest that Germany might be a promising market for cultured meat. In contrast, Italy's recent ban on cultured meat (Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, 2023) may have negatively affected public perception, creating a significant barrier to its acceptance among Italian consumers.

4.3. Drivers of the consumption of meat alternatives

Another aim of the present study was to examine how consumer characteristics influence the consumption of traditional (e.g., tofu and falafel) and new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks) in the four European countries. In general, it was found that the consumption of meat alternatives is still significantly lower than that of conventional meat. While traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel) are rarely consumed across all countries, new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, chunks) are more frequently consumed in Italy and Serbia than in Germany and Finland. These cross-country differences may potentially be influenced by income disparities, suggesting that the adoption of meat alternatives might be driven more by economic factors than by health or environmental concerns (de Boer & Aiking, 2018). Culinary traditions may also play an important role in this regard. For instance, the rich tradition of plant-based dishes in Italy (Parasecoli, 2004) and the Orthodox fasting practices in Serbia, during which meat is avoided (Lackenby, 2024), may facilitate the adoption of meat alternatives in these countries. In contrast, traditional diets in northern and western European countries are more centered around

animal-based products, which could pose a significant barrier to replacing meat with plant-based alternatives (de Boer & Aiking, 2018).

The regression models demonstrated the impact of individual factors on the consumption of meat alternatives. Consistent with previous studies, meat alternatives were found to be consumed more frequently by younger individuals (Elzerman et al., 2021; Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019; Slade, 2018). However, while earlier research has shown that women are more likely than men to consume meat alternatives (Elzerman et al., 2021; Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019), the present study only observed a significant effect of sex in Finland and Serbia. The findings contradict previous research and indicate that men are more likely to consume meat alternatives more frequently than women.

Moreover, meat commitment had a significant effect on the consumption of traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel) in all countries, but only on the consumption of new meat-like meat alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks) in Finland. In Germany and Serbia, the consumption of this type of meat alternatives was instead explained by meat alternative rejection levels. These findings may reflect the extent to which the two types of meat alternatives imitate meat, which in turn influences consumers' perception of them as meat replacements (Fischer et al., 2023). Compared to tofu and falafel, plant-based mince, burgers, and chunks are more similar to meat in terms of appearance, preparation method, and product names. This similarity makes them more likely to be rejected by individuals who are skeptical of meat alternatives (i.e., those with high meat alternative rejection levels). Conversely, products such as tofu and falafel are more likely to be rejected by individuals with high meat commitment levels due to their lack of functional similarities with meat.

Finally, in contrast to previous studies showing that food neophobia acts as a barrier to the acceptance of plant-based meat alternatives (e.g., burger patties) (Michel, Knaapila, et al., 2021b; van Dijk et al., 2023), the present study found that food neophobia affected the consumption of traditional meat alternatives (e.g., tofu and falafel) more than new meat-like alternatives (e.g., mince, burgers, and chunks). One possible explanation for this finding is that products such as tofu and falafel can be associated with non-European cuisines (Asian and Middle Eastern, respectively), which may trigger neophobic responses. In contrast, plant-based mince, burgers, and chunks are designed to mimic familiar meat products, thereby potentially reducing the impact of food neophobia. This suggests that consumers may not consider this new generation of meat alternatives to be novel foods, potentially also due to increased exposure to these products. Overall, this can be seen as a positive development for increasing consumer acceptance of this type of meat alternatives.

4.4. Limitations and future research

While the present study provides valuable insights into consumer acceptance of a wide variety of proteins for meat alternatives, some limitations need to be acknowledged. First, European consumers have limited or no access to some of the assessed protein sources, including algae, insects, and cultured meat. This may have influenced the results, as participants may have found it difficult to rate their expectations for meat alternatives made from these sources, particularly in comparison to more familiar proteins such as potatoes. Moreover, while consumer expectations play a significant role in the willingness to try a product, it is important that the product meets these expectations for it to succeed. Thus, it would be beneficial to conduct additional sensory studies with currently available protein sources to assess the alignment between consumer expectations and actual taste evaluations. Finally, this study did not examine the relative importance of the protein source compared to other product attributes such as price or nutritional and sensory characteristics. Therefore, trade-off studies are needed to better understand the role of the protein source in consumers' overall decision-making process.

5. Conclusion

The consumption of meat alternatives among meat eaters in Germany, Finland, Italy, and Serbia remains relatively low. However, the findings of this study indicate that certain protein sources for use in meat alternatives have greater potential in terms of consumer acceptance than others. Potato, rice, and peas were identified as the most promising protein sources in all countries, along with almonds in Germany and Serbia, oats in Finland, and lentils in Italy. The findings indicate that familiarity and regional culinary traditions influence consumer preferences and should therefore be considered when developing meat alternatives to make them more attractive to consumers. Finally, the study revealed low expectations for algae and cultured meat and found that insects are the least accepted protein source among European consumers. This presents a major challenge to the successful integration of these protein sources into the European market.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kirsten Pronk: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Bruno Etter:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Fabienne Michel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michael Siegrist:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethical statement

Before participating, subjects were presented with information about the aim of the study, the general procedure for completing the questionnaire, details about anonymity and data protection, information about the subjects' right to withdraw at any point during the study, and the researcher's contact information. Participation in the study required the subject's informed consent. Participants were compensated with points according to the panel provider's compensation system. The study was approved by the ETH Zurich Ethics Commission on September 20, 2023 (proposal No EK 2023-N-234).

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Declaration of competing interest

None.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2025.108246>.

Data availability

All data is made available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16419515>

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